

SPLiT: Standardized Prediction of Lithium Titers Using Routine Clinical Monitoring Data

Preregistered-style summary

Objective. The SPLiT study aims to develop and validate a library of statistical and machine-learning models for (a) standardizing measured serum lithium concentrations to an equivalent 12-hour level and (b) predicting individual therapeutic lithium doses using data obtained from routine clinical monitoring in patients with affective spectrum disorders.

Primary confirmatory hypothesis. A hierarchy of models with increasing predictor informativeness demonstrates a monotonic improvement in predictive performance: extended models incorporating demographic characteristics, anthropometry, renal function, and treatment-related parameters outperform baseline models in both standardization of serum lithium concentration to the 12-hour equivalent and prediction of individual therapeutic lithium dose.

Study design. Retrospective, observational (non-interventional), cohort study with a cross-sectional analytical framework. One serum lithium measurement per participant is used for the primary analysis.

Population. Adult patients (≥ 18 years) with bipolar affective disorder type I or II, recurrent depressive disorder, or schizoaffective disorder receiving lithium therapy, with documented serum lithium concentration and blood sampling time. Patients with chronic kidney disease stage ≥ 3 or missing key data are excluded.

Sample size. Based on a previously reported Pearson correlation coefficient $|r| = 0.30$ between serum lithium concentration and time since last dose, sample size was calculated using Fisher's z-transformation (two-sided $\alpha = 0.05$). Required sample sizes are $n = 85$ (80% power), $n = 113$ (90% power), and $n = 139$ (95% power).

Statistical analysis. Model performance will be evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation and standard predictive metrics (RMSE, MAE, R^2). Comparative performance of models of increasing complexity will be assessed on held-out data.

Deviations. Any deviations from this preregistered analytical plan will be explicitly documented and justified in subsequent publications.

Status. This document is published to ensure transparency and reproducibility and records the analytical plan prior to primary data analysis.